

The Surface Digital Grain Size (DGS) Protocol (Part 1: Data Collection Field Guide)

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This field guide outlines a standardised approach to surface digital grain size (DGS) data collection, facilitating the rapid characterisation of coarse and mixed sediment coastal environments

Overview:

Obtaining robust grain size distribution data for coarse and mixed-sediment environments presents significant logistical and financial challenges when relying on traditional methods (e.g physical sieving and caliper measurements). This document details a cost-effective and rapid approach for the high-resolution acquisition of spatially continuous sediment distribution data, designated as the Surface DGS Protocol. Equipment specifications, calibration, sampling strategy, and field execution standards required to ensure statistical validity and data reproducibility are outlined below.

This protocol was designed as part of PhD research directly aligned with the NERC funded [#gravelbeach Project \(Link\)](#). The method has been used extensively in Work Packages 1, 2 and 3 of the project. A dataset comprising of around 20,000 images has now been collected across 60 locations around the UK coastline and forms a crucial component of a new beach classification scheme for gravel beaches. The approach has also been adopted for characterising the grain size distributions of rubble tracks on atoll islands.

1. Motivation & Objectives:

The primary objective of this protocol is to overcome the inherent spatial sparsity and time constraints associated with physical sediment sampling on coarse material beaches. By standardising a digital acquisition workflow, this method enables:

- **High-Spatial Resolution:** Collection of grain size distribution dataset across large spatial extents (>1 km) which would be infeasible with manual sampling.
- **Cost-Effective:** Makes use of consumer-grade technology (total equipment cost ~£550) to reduce barriers to implementation for coastal monitoring programmes.

2. Equipment List & Links:

The assembly is custom-built, designed to be lightweight for portability and stability on uneven surfaces. Links to examples of the necessary components to build the DGS system are provided below (Figure 1).

2.1. Camera:

- **Camera:** GoPro HERO 11 or GoPro HERO 13. Selected for its high-resolution picture quality, robust stabilisation, and integrated Global Positioning System (GPS). **Note: GoPro HERO 12 does not have inbuilt GPS. [Camera Link](#)**
- **Remote Trigger:** GoPro "The Remote" (Bluetooth-enabled) to allow rapid image capture. [Remote Link](#)

- **Storage:** SanDisk Extreme PRO 256GB microSDXC. [SD Card Link](#)
- **SD Card Reader:** [SD Reader Link](#)
- **Power:** Spare GoPro Enduro batteries recommended and dual-battery charger. [Batteries & Charger Link](#)

2.2 Survey Pole:

- **Extension Pole:** 2m Extending Pole. Any lightweight telescoping pole that will be stable at full extension. [Emlid Survey Pole Link \(expensive option\)](#) or [Harris Extension Pole Link \(budget option\)](#)
- **Mounting Boom:** Elgato 125 cm Multi Mount. This acts as the horizontal boom mount, allowing the camera to be offset to prevent foot/shadow inclusion in the frame. [Mounting Boom Link](#)
- **Mount Connection:** HSU Cold Shoe Adapter (1/4" thread) with locking key to secure the camera housing to the mount. [Shoe Adapter Link](#)
- **Levelling:** A pole bubble level to verify vertical alignment (nadir viewing angle). [Bubble Level Link](#)
- **Floodlight:** Suptig LED High Power Dimmable Waterproof Video Light (for low light surveying) [LED Floodlight Link](#) & [LED Mounting Bracket Link](#)

Figure 1: Equipment and assembly requirements for DGS Survey Camera.

3. Configuration & Calibration:

3.1. Camera Settings:

To ensure data quality and suitability for analysis, the following camera configuration is required:

- **Lens Mode: Photo Linear (L) Mode.** Removes the "fisheye" barrel distortion typical of wide-angle action cameras.
- **Preset:** Configured to "Last Used: **Photo Linear (L) Mode** " to maintain settings between power cycles.
- **GPS:** Enabled (Verified via test capture prior to survey – check GPS icon is highlighted white in top left corner of camera display – walk around to get GPS fix if icon doesn't highlight initially).
- **Updates:** Firmware should be updated via GoPro Quik App regularly.

3.2. Camera Mount Assembly:

The camera mount is attached to the extension pole to create an inverted 'L' shape. The horizontal arm should be extended to ensure the base of vertical pole is excluded from the camera's field of view (FOV). All locking mechanisms must be tightened to minimise flex, particularly when operating at maximum extension (H4).

3.3. Adaptive Sampling Resolution (H1–H4 Protocol):

The protocol employs an **adaptive height approach (Figure 2)**, designed to maintain statistical validity when surveying environments with highly variable sediment grain size distributions (e.g. pure and mixed gravel beaches).

The camera height is designed to be adjusted to satisfy two "Golden Rules":

1. **Resolution:** Individual grains must be resolvable by eye (approx. >20 pixels diameter per grain).
2. **Population:** The capture area must be large enough to contain >300 grains per image.

Table 1: Standardised Survey Heights and Target Sediment Ranges

Height Code	Camera Height	Target Grain Size Range	Approx. Resolution*
H1	0.30 m	Fine Gravel (2 – 20 mm)	0.080 mm/px
H2	0.50 m	Medium Gravel (5 – 40 mm)	0.165 mm/px
H3	1.00 m	Coarse Gravel (10 – 80 mm)	0.370 mm/px
H4	2.00 m	Cobbles (20 – 160 mm)	0.700 mm/px

Note: Resolution must be verified via the calibration procedure outlined in Section 3.4 for your specific camera set up (See Figure 3 for measurement guide).

Figure 2: Camera height settings and appropriate grain size ranges. Use upper limit as the guide for determining height.

3.4 Resolution Calibration (The "Resolution Bubbles" Method):

To derive real-world units (mm) from pixel data, the method requires height-specific calibration.

- **Procedure:** A printout of "Resolution Bubbles" of known dimensions should be photographed on a level surface (see last page for print out).
- **Replication:** Multiple independent images should be captured at each of the four designated survey heights.
- **Calculation:** The spatial resolution (R) in mm/pixel is calculated as:

$$R = \frac{\text{Actual Width of Object (mm)}}{\text{Pixel Width of Object in Image (px)}}$$

- The final resolution for each height should be taken as the average of all replicate images of the resolution bubbles.

Figure 3: Measuring height settings for DGS Camera. Measure from pole foot to base of camera mounting boom.

4. Sampling Strategy:

To ensure the dataset is representative, a systematic stratified sampling approach is outlined below:

4.1. Profile Distribution:

- **Spacing:** 6 cross-shore profiles should be spaced at **50 m intervals** from the centre of the survey area (P1 – P6) (Figure 4).
- **Extent:** For study sites >1000 m in length, a second sampling set (e.g., P7–P12) is recommended to maintain representative sampling density if time allows.
- **Georeferencing:** If an RTK GPS is not available, a handheld GPS or Mobile Phone GPS should be used to navigate to pre-defined profile coordinates.

The internal GPS of the GoPro should be accurate to a few metres, but it is best to record metadata to ensure accuracy and to mitigate against possible GPS dropout.

- To map where sediment composition changes to a mixed zone the transitions should be captured by taking a photo before and after the composition change.

Figure 4: Survey sampling strategy. Blue points show the minimum expected sample for cross-shore transect. Red zones illustrate how to survey additional points to capture the transitions from pure to mixed sediment zones.

4.2. Cross-Shore Stratification:

Sampling density within a profile is dictated by the beach morphology (Figure 5):

- **Single Slope Profiles:** A minimum of **5 equally spaced sample points** collected from the back beach to the Mean Low Water Spring (MLWS).
- **Composite Slope Profiles:** Sampling is split to capture:
 - **Upper Beach (Steep):** Minimum of **5 equally spaced samples**.
 - **Lower Beach (Low-angle):** Minimum of **3 equally spaced samples**.
- You will likely take closer to 10 samples per transect on the single slope / upper beach section off your survey area. A **good rule of thumb is to take a sample, pace out 5 metres** and take the next sample.

Figure 5: Example of DGS sampling strategy for single slope and composite slope gravel beaches.

4.3. Sample Point Redundancy:

At every sample point, 4 overlapping images (approx. 50% overlap) should be captured (Figure 6). This redundancy mitigates the risk of single-image outliers and allows for the 4 images to be averaged to produce a single, robust value for each sample location.

Figure 6: Example of how to capture 4 overlapping images per DGS sample.

5. Field Survey Procedure:

5.1. Execution:

- **Orientation:** The surveyor should stand square to the beach profile. If available a "spotter" can be useful to verify the FOV is perpendicular to the beach slope (Figure 7). However, once practiced you will be able to do this yourself.

Figure 7: Example of keeping camera FOV perpendicular to beach surface.

- **Levelling & Stability:** The bubble level should be used to ensure the pole is upright (nadir view) (Figure 8). The camera needs to be held static to prevent motion blur, although GoPro has excellent image stability.

Figure 8: Example of how to use bubble level to ensure survey pole is upright (Nadir view). Left panel: pole is upright (Green). Right panel: pole is leaning towards the right (Red).

- **Lighting & Shadowing:** The surveyor must position themselves such that their shadow falls *behind* the rig. Surveys should ideally be conducted under overcast conditions to minimise hard shadows, which can interfere with algorithm accuracy.

5.2. Checkpointing & Metadata:

- **Checkpoint Photos:** At the start of each profile, a photo of a notebook (displaying Profile ID and Height Code, e.g., "P1 H1") or just a distinct landscape shot should be taken. This serves as a visual check in the raw images to prevent data misattribution during processing.
- **Remember to ensure camera date and time is correct before starting your survey.**
- **Field Logs:** A manual log should be maintained during surveying, recording:
 - Profile start and end time (time of first photo).
 - Camera height setting used for the profile.
 - Any deviations/errors or retakes.

6. Data Processing & Algorithms

Detailed workflows and explanation of how to process the data collected using the above method will be provided in pending published academic works. Following publication of the research associated with this field guide, a second document will be provided that outlines the necessary data pre-processing steps, the selection of appropriate algorithms and steps for calibration. Direct links to python scripts for processing will also be provided.

Print this page out (A4) and use the bubbles to calculate the resolution for each of the 4 camera height intervals (mm/pixels).

Take photo on a level surface and use bubble level to ensure pole is upright.